

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
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MUNDARIJA

EKSPORT VA IMPORT OPERATSIYALARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH: TAHLIL VA AUDIT	10
Urinboev Bexruz Zoir o'g'li, Misirov Asliddin Mamasobirovich	
QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA YASHIL INNOVATSIYALARNING ROLI	15
Jabborov Muhammad Sanjarovich, Djurayeva Dilnoza Davron qizi, Song Jichung	
RAQAMLASHTIRISH SHAROITIDA O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING RIVOJLANISH OMILLARI VA MAKROIQTISODIY TA'SIRI.....	21
Xoliqulova Ra'no Sherali qizi, Berdiyev Nazirjon Abduvoseyevich	
КУЛЬТУРНЫЙ ТУРИЗМ КАК ФАКТОР УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	25
Ахтамов Огабек Улугбек угли, Фахритдинов Амриддин Фазлитдинович, Саидмуродов Жонибек Жахонгирович, Саттарова Зухра Илхомовна	
DAVLATNING YASHIL INVESTITSIYALAR ORQALI IQTISODIYOTNI TARTIBGA SOLISH SIYOSATI.....	31
Sharipboyev Hasanboy Marks o'g'li, Shodmonov Ruslan G'olib o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTON IQTISODIYOTI O'SISHIDA TRANSPORT INFRATUZILMASINING STRATEGIK O'RNI: PREZIDENT MUHOJIRATNOMASI ASOSIDA ILMIY TAHLIL	35
Ma'rupov Zahiriddin Feruzovich, Kurbanova Mehriniso Nematjanovna	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASIDAGI BIZNES-SUBYEKTLARINI BAHOLASH: ESG MEZONLARI ASOSIDA BARQARORLIK INDEKSINI ISHLAB CHIQISH VA O'ZBEKISTON AMALIYOTI	39
Po'latov Orzubek Fazliddin o'g'li, Haqnazarova Yulduz Juraqulovna	
ФИНАНСОВЫЕ ИНСТИТУТЫ КАК ФАКТОР МОДЕРНИЗАЦИИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	43
Мукарова Сарвиноз Маликовна, Каримова Азиза Махомадризовна	
AKSIZ SOLIG'I TUSHUMLARINING O'ZBEKISTON RESPUBLIKASI BUDJET DAROMADLARIDAGI ULUSHI: 2020–2024-YILLAR BO'YICHA IQTISODIY TAHLILI	49
Karimov Diyorbek, Abdurashidov Abdusamad	
O'ZBEKISTON SOLIQ TIZIMIDA RAQAMLASHTIRISH JARAYONLARINING SOLIQ TUSHUMLARI VA FUQAROLARNING SOLIQ INTIZOMIGA TA'SIRI	55
Maxkamova Dildora Shavkat qizi, Ergashev Shavkat Maxkamovich	
ИНТЕГРАЦИЯ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ЦЕННОСТЕЙ В МАРКЕТИНГОВЫЕ КОММУНИКАЦИИ КОМПАНИЙ.....	59
Рахимжонов Абдор Марифжанович, Кахрамонов Хуршид Шухратович	
BOZOR IQTISODIYOTIDA UMUMIY TALAB VA UMUMIY TAKLIF	66
O'ktamova Shaxruza Abror qizi, Norboyev Odil Abrayevich	
RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA IJTIMOYIY TARMOQLAR ORQALI MARKETINGNI RIVOJLANTIRISH USULLARI (O'ZBEKISTONDAGI YIRIK BRENDLAR MISOLIDA).....	70
Axmedova Robiya Rustamovna, Kadirova Sharafat Amonovna	
MINTAQANING INNOVATSION IQTISODIY RIVOJLANISH TENDENSIYASI	76
Rushana Taxirova, F.U.Umarov	
SAMARQAND VILOYATI UCHUN TURIZM MAHSULOTLARINI YARATISH	83
Alimardonova D.T., Tursunova G.R.	

BUXORO VILOYATINING MADANIY VA TARIXIY MEROSI ASOSIDA KREATIV TURIZM MAHSULOTLARINI YARATISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	91
Davronova G.O., Tursunova G.R.	
MAIN DIRECTIONS OF ECONOMIC AND SOCIAL EFFICIENCY IN SERVICE ENTERPRISES	96
Ilamonov Mehroj Akbar o'g'li, Xayitov Jamshid Xolvoyevich	
KREDIT MEXANIZMINING ELEMENTLARI O'RTASIDAGI ALOQADORLIKNI TA'MINLASH YO'LLARI.....	102
Alimov Umid Xamid o'g'li, Umarov F. U.	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATIDA EKSPORTNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA QISHLOQ XO'JALIGI MAHSULOTLARINING AHAMIYATI.....	109
Mamanazarov Javohir Kamolovich, Xurramov Ramazon Allayor o'g'li	
XALQARO BANKLAR TOMONIDAN INVESTITSION LOYIHALARNI KREDITLASH MEXANIZMI VA UNING IQTISODIY TA'SIRI	115
Boltayeva O'g'iloy, Tuxsanov Eldor Dilmurod o'g'li	
STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV HISOBI VA UNING USLUBIYOTINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH MASALALARI	119
Sharipova Mohinur, Uralova Sevara, Zaripova Sayohat Zafarovna	
XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA RAQAMLASHTIRISH VA EKOLOGIK BARQARORLIK: ZAMONAVIY INTEGRATSIYA YO'NALISHLARI.....	123
A'zamova Feruza Abduholiq qizi, Kuldoshev Lazizjon Sharifovich	
DIRECTIONS FOR IMPROVING PUBLIC WELFARE AND REDUCING POVERTY.....	127
Jumanazarov Ro'zmurod, Rabbimov Elbek Abdulloevich, Ergashev Olloyor Furqat o'g'li	
THE EVOLUTION OF E-COMMERCE IN UZBEKISTAN: TRENDS, DRIVERS, AND FUTURE PROSPECTS.....	132
Madina Abdujabborova, Nozima Zufarova	
IQTISODIY TRANSFORMATSIYA JARAYONINI BOSHDAN KECHIRAYOTGAN MAMLAKATLARDA INVESTITSIYA BOZORLARINING SHAKLLANISHI VA RIVOJLANISH ISTIQBOLLARI	136
Hayot Abduqodirov, G'olib Baxriddinov, Karjavova Xurshida Abdumalikovna	
WAYS TO ENSURE THE FINANCIAL STABILITY OF ENTERPRISES THROUGH THE USE OF MONETARY AND CREDIT INSTRUMENTS IN BANKS	141
Mustafaeva Khurliman Azat kizi, Baymuratova Zina Aqilbekovna	
KICHIK BIZNES SUBEKTLARINING INNOVATSION FAOLIYATINI RAG'BATLANTIRISH YO'LLARI	147
Xakimova Go'zal Akbar qizi, Xolmirzayev Ulug'bek Abdulazizovich	
TAX SYSTEM FOR SMALL BUSINESSES	152
A. Juzbaev, Davletyarova Guldana	
WAYS TO DEVELOP THE PRACTICE OF USING INNOVATION IN BANKS.....	156
Umedov Abdullo, Khodjimamedov Akmal Ashurovich	
IMPROVING THE ACCOUNTING OF INCOME FROM CORE ACTIVITIES IN SAM GLASS LLC.....	161
Usmanov Shakhzod Shokhrukhovich, Musaeva Shoira Azimovna	

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and digital metrics. Mass surveillance methods were used to collect and analyze data from social media platforms.

Analysis and results

Income received as a result of the transfer of assets for use by other business entities, generating interest, royalties and other income, should be recognized on the following basis:

- Interest is recognized based on a time relationship that takes into account the actual income from the asset;
- Royalties are recognized on an accrual basis in accordance with the terms of the agreement;
- Dividends are recognized when the shareholders' rights to receive payment are established.

In cases:

- The existence of a probability that the economic entity will receive economic benefits associated with the transaction;
- Estimate the amount of income with a greater degree of reliability;

Revenue is recognized on the following basis:

Income is recognized only when it is probable that the economic entity will receive economic benefits associated with the transaction.

Income accounting should be organized in such a way that the following information can be disclosed in the financial statements:

1. The accounting policies adopted for recognizing revenue, including the methods adopted for determining the stage of completion of transactions.

2. The amount of each material category of income recognized during the period, including income received from:

- Sales of goods;
- Percent;
- Royalty;
- Dividends;

3. The amount of income received from the exchange of goods or services included in each significant category of income.

4. To reflect exchange rate differences arising from the revaluation of foreign exchange balance sheet items on the last day of the reporting month at the exchange rate of the Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the enterprise applies the method of direct attribution to the results of financial and economic activities:

- positive exchange rate difference – to the accounts recording income from financial activities;
- negative exchange rate difference – to the accounts for recording expenses on financial activities.

Below are typical accounting entries reflecting income from the company's core activities, based on contracts concluded with counterparties and actual shipment of products (Table 1):

Table 1. Accounting entries for reflecting income from core activities¹

No.	Type of operation	Debit	Credit	Amount (UZS)	Counterparty / Agreement
1	Sales of products	4010	9010	22,053,571.43	CHANDIR TOMORQA XIZMATI / Agreement No. 459 dated 12/22/2023
2	Sales of products	4010	9010	89,285,714.29	OOO ORDER / Agreement No. 72 dated 02/03/2023
3	Sales of products	4010	9010	8,928,571.43	ELNUR FARID MARKED / Agreement No. 10 dated 01/04/2023
4	Selling your own goods	4010	9020	94,803,571.43	OOO «OK-GLASS» / Agreement No. 16 dated 01/09/2024
5	Sales of products	4010	9010	4,464,285.71	SANJAR - SARDOR AKFA ROMBLARI / Agreement No. 5 dated 01/05/2024
6	Sales of products	4010	9010	133,928,700.90	TAMIRLASH QURISH SERVICE LLC / Agreement No. 26 dated 01/10/2024
7	Sales of products	4010	9010	28,656,450.00	STAINLESS-STEEL SAMARKAND / Agreement No. 2 dated 01/04/2024

¹ Source: Author's own development.

8	Sales of products	4010	9010	17,857,142.86	«Universal Info Servis» / Agreement No. 461 dated December 22, 2023
9	Sales of products	4010	9010	133,928,571.43	MUSAFFO INTER INJINERING / Agreement No. 439 dated 12/19/2023
10	Selling your own goods	4010	9020	89,285,714.29	MCHJ MAGNIT SAVDO SERVIS / Agreement No. 11 dated 01/09/2024
11	Sales of products	4010	9010	5,312,500.00	OOO «Eternity Construction Internation» / Agreement No. 206 dated 05/01/2023

In addition to cashless payments, SAM GLASS LLC accepts payment for products via terminals and in cash. Such receipts are reflected in the following accounts (Table 2) [14]:

Table 2. Transactions for payments via terminal and in cash²

No.	Type of operation	Debit	Credit	Amount (UZS)	Note
1	Revenue through the terminal (wholesale)	5710	9020	235,680,357.14	Cash in transit (POS)
2	Cash receipts (wholesale)	5010	9020	2,678,571.43	Cash register
3	Revenue through the terminal (retail)	5710	9020	231,083,029.46	Cash in transit (POS)
4	Cash receipts (retail)	5010	9020	1,785,714.29	Cash register

Thus, income accounting at SAM GLASS LLC is carried out in full compliance with regulatory requirements. All income is properly documented and reflected in the appropriate accounting accounts. This allows for transparent financial control, reliable reporting, and effective cash flow management.

In the accounting records of SAM GLASS LLC, revenues not related to the sale of products, goods, and services are recognized as other revenues. They are reported separately from the company's core activities in accounts group 9300, in accordance with the Regulation on Cost Structure (Appendix to PKM No. 54 of February 5, 1999) and Article 132 of the Tax Code.

Such income includes:

- profit from disposal of fixed assets (9310),
- profit from disposal of other assets (9320),
- fines, penalties, forfeits (9330),
- profit of previous years (9340),
- income from short-term rentals (9350),
- income from writing off accounts payable or depositor debt (9360),
- income of service enterprises (9370),
- gratuitous financial assistance (9380),
- other operating income (9390).

In practice, SAM GLASS LLC records other income primarily through account 9350 – Income from short-term rentals, which is reflected by the following entries (Table 3) [6]:

Table 3. Accounting for other income³

Operation	Debit	Credit	Amount (UZS)
OMONBOYEV AHROR FARXODJONOVICH, Agreement No. 1523564 dated 11/01/2023	4890	9350	1,915,178.57
«PARADISE PHARM» MCHJ, Agreement No. 1 dated 01/01/2023	4890	9350	1,000,000.00
SHARAFITDINOV SARVAR SHUXRATOVICH, Agreement No. 1565093 dated 01/01/2024	4890	9350	2,357,142.86
OMONBOYEV AHROR FARXODJONOVICH, Agreement No. 1523564 dated 11/01/2023	4890	9350	1,915,178.57

² Source: Author's own development.

³ Source: Author's own development.

«PARADISE PHARM» MCHJ, Agreement No. 1 dated 01/01/2023	4890	9350	1,000,000.00
SHARAFITDINOV SARVAR SHUXRATOVICH, Agreement No. 1565093 dated 01/01/2024	4890	9350	2,357,142.86
OMONBOYEV AHROR FARXODJONOVICH, Agreement No. 1523564 dated 11/01/2023	4890	9350	1,915,178.57
«PARADISE PHARM» MCHJ, Agreement No. 1 dated 01/01/2023	4890	9350	1,000,000.00
SHARAFITDINOV SARVAR SHUXRATOVICH, Agreement No. 1565093 dated 01/01/2024	4890	9350	2,357,142.86

The main principle of accounting for expenses at SAM GLASS LLC is the principle of compliance with income, according to which only those costs that led to the receipt of revenue in the current reporting period are reflected in the accounting.

Accounts for recording the cost of sold products (goods, works, services) (9100).

To systematize information on expenses related to the sale of products, goods, works and services, the enterprise uses account group 9100 - "Accounts for recording the cost of sold products (goods, works, services)".

Applicable accounts:

- 9110— Cost of finished goods sold;
- 9120— Cost of goods sold;
- 9130— Cost of work performed and services rendered;
- 9140— Acquisition/purchase of inventory items during periodic accounting;
- 9150— Adjustment of inventory items during periodic accounting.

When selling products or goods, the corresponding cost is reflected in the debit of accounts 9110, 9120, 9130 in correspondence with inventory accounts: 2810, 2910, 2920, etc. Depending on the applied method of accounting for inventories, accounts 9140 and 9150 are also used. At the end of the reporting period, accounts 9110–9150 are closed through account 9910 – "Final financial result".

Examples of accounting entries in SAM GLASS LLC for accounts 9100 (Table 4):

Table 4. Postings to cost accounting accounts sold products (goods, works, services) ⁴

Operation	Dt	CT	Sum
Service warehouse - Glass cut to customer dimensions	9110	2810	848.214
Service warehouse - Tempered glass	9110	2810	744.047
Service warehouse - Sheet glass M0 6 mm, 3600×2600 mm (784,185 pcs.)	9120	2910	35,708,430.37
Service warehouse - Clear sheet glass 10 mm, 3210×2550 mm (257,179 pcs.)	9120	2910	18,728,878.08
Store - Calculating Trade Markups	2980	9120	11,350,425.17
Store - Write-off of sales	9120	2920	235,680,357.14
Store - Write-off of sales	9120	2920	2,678,571.43

Period Expense Accounts (9400)

In the SAM GLASS LLC accounting system, period expense accounts (group 9400) are designed to summarize information on expenses not directly related to the production process. This includes product sales expenses, administrative costs, other operating expenses, as well as reporting period expenses that will be excluded from taxation in the future. In accordance with the company's internal accounting policy, the following account structure is used:

- 9410 «Selling expenses»– reflects costs associated with the sale of goods and services;
- 9420 «Administrative expenses»– covers all management and business expenses;
- 9430 «Other operating expenses» – records losses and non-production costs;
- 9440 «Expenses of the reporting period excluded from the taxable base in the future»– temporary differences that are subject to exclusion from taxation in subsequent periods (Table 5).

⁴ Source: Author's own development.

Table 5. Postings to period expense accounts⁵

Operation	Debit	Credit	Amount (sum)	Note
Bank services	9430	5110	6,095,256.45	Bank service fee
Tax assessment (other expenses): water use tax	9430	6410	13,330,400.00	Water tax
Tax assessment: property tax	9430	6410	5,095,189.11	Property tax for legal entities
Tax assessment: land tax	9430	6410	5,095,189.11	Land tax
Other tax liabilities	9430	6410	10,250.00	Other charges
Write-off of methane gas from the warehouse	9430	1030	2,864,066.73	987 m ³ of methane gas
Accrual of the Unified Social Tax on administrative expenses	9430	6520	148,200.00	Unified social payment (administration)
Accrual of unified social tax on sales expenses	9410	6520	167,400.00	Unified social payment (implementation)
Payroll – Vakhobov Zh.N.	9410	6710	1,395,000.00	Salary (sales)
Payroll – Zhabborova H.T.	9430	6710	1,235,000.00	Salaries (other expenses)
Payroll calculation – Sharipov A.A.	9420	6710	2,250,000.00	Administration salaries
Payroll – Norov I.O.	9420	6710	2,033,000.00	Administration salaries

In SAM GLASS LLC's accounting records, expenses unrelated to core operations are reflected separately from production and administrative costs. These expenses include:

- expenses related to financial activities (interest on loans, exchange rate differences, losses from revaluation of securities, etc.);
- extraordinary losses arising from accidents, fires, natural disasters and other unforeseen situations.

Financial expenses

To summarize information on expenses related to financial transactions, account group 9600 "Expenses on financial activities" is used.

These accounts reflect:

- interest paid on loans and credits;
- negative exchange rate differences on transactions with foreign currency;
- losses from revaluation of financial investments;
- other expenses related to the financial activities of the enterprise.

Extraordinary losses

Extraordinary losses include losses from events outside the normal course of business, such as:

- natural disasters;
- fires and accidents;
- emergency measures to prevent disasters and eliminate their consequences.

These expenses are reflected in account 9720 "Extraordinary Losses." The decision to classify expenses as extraordinary is made based on their unpredictability and rarity within the organization's operating conditions.

Closing accounts

At the end of the reporting period, the balances of all expense accounts, including accounts 9600 and 9720, are written off to account 9910 "Final financial result" in order to form the final profit or loss for the reporting period.

At SAM GLASS LLC, which processes, tempers, and recycles glass, income tax accounting is conducted in accordance with the Tax Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan and National Accounting Standards.

Main accounting accounts (Table 6):

- 9810– Income tax expenses;
- 9820– Expenses for other tax liabilities calculated from profit;
- 6410–Outstanding payments to the budget (by type);
- 9910–The final financial result (profit or loss).

⁵ Source: Author's own development.

Table 6. Income tax transactions⁶

No.	Date and time	Description of the operation	Debit	Credit	Amount (UZS)
1	March 31, 2024, 12:00:05 PM	Calculation of income tax	9820	6410	47,160,073.00
2	March 31, 2024, 12:00:00 PM	Formation of the final financial result	9910	9820	47,160,073.00

Payroll accounting at SAM GLASS LLC, as with any business entity, is carried out in strict compliance with the Labor Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Tax Code, and national accounting standards. The company is responsible for the accurate accrual, withholding, payment, and accounting of all employee payments, as well as the timely transfer of mandatory taxes and contributions.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The specifics of accounting at SAM GLASS LLC: the accounting system, methods and programs used, as well as the documentation procedure are clearly visible.

Practical aspects of accounting: this is the process of registering and writing off goods, accounting for accounts receivable and payable, as well as the preparation of primary documents.

The role of accounting in an organization's activities: it shows how accounting ensures financial transparency and control, as well as how it influences management decision-making.

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⁶ Source: Author's own development.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

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1-Maxsus son. Bakalavr talabalarining maqolalari to'plami

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